

**THE ROLE OF PRACTICAL EXERCISES TO IMPROVE THE
LOGICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.**

Kelimanova Zhanar Meirambaevna, Piyas Zarina

Taraz Regional University named after M.Kh.Dulaty, Kazakhstan.

Annotation: Developing in mental activity of students is an important part of their development as personality. Therefore, when performing creative tasks, students must be taught to do thinking functions. That's why, when assigning tasks to student and the tasks should be selected, collected, compared and grouped in such a way that they develop logical thinking.

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Аннотация: Развитие мыслительной деятельности учащихся является важной частью их личностного развития. Поэтому при выполнении творческих заданий учащихся необходимо обучать выполнению мыслительных функций. Вот почему при назначении заданий ученику следует подбирать, собирать, сравнивать и группировать задания таким образом, чтобы они развивали логическое мышление.

Ключевые слова: Развитие, мыслительная деятельность учащихся, развитие, творческие задания.

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p It is clear that the current global restructuring, rapid computerization and changes in the field of education create the need to improve the quality of teaching. Human society New technologies were used to increase the effectiveness of the training process. It is combined with the aim of increasing the logical and creative potential of the student and preparing the young generation to live in new social conditions. Currently, the process of computerization of education is underway. The use of information and communication technology, new learning methods through the computer network is spreading. Modern requirements require the use of various techniques and methods at the level of personal development and expansion of cognitive dimensions. That is why I believe that exercises that improve students'

thinking skills with the help of information technology have a special place in primary school. This is because improving the skills of a child who has just entered school, raising educational interest to a creative level, developing logical thinking are among the tasks of primary school teachers. After all, the initial period is a very convenient time for the development of the students' activity. Completing logical tasks and exercises is very important to develop students' creativity. The student's logical thinking develops in reasoning, information acquisition and language learning.

Developing in mental activity of students is an important part of their development as personality. Therefore, when performing creative tasks, students must be taught to do thinking functions. That's why, when assigning tasks to student and the tasks should be selected, collected, compared and grouped in such a way that they develop logical thinking. For example, the following exercises help develop verbal and logical thinking: "Find more" methodology. Shows the child's ability to separate and generalize important parts. This method can be used in any languages and world studies classes during consolidation and revision periods. The task can be presented in a picture, in kind or in writing. The "collection" methodology is effective for the development of thought analysis and accumulation operations.

Name a word or phrase that summarizes the suggested words:

1. October- November
2. Carp- pike
3. Summer- autumn
4. Oak- birch
5. Cucumber- tomato
6. Ant- beetle

At the same time, methods that develop thinking can be used in the form of a game. For example, the game "Say the opposite". In this game, it is useful to use words that have the opposite meaning in the past tense. For instance, full-thin, black-white, hot-cold, empty-full, etc. "Similarities and differences". Students are

encouraged to compare different objects and concepts. "Identify from another perspective".

Find the other side of a given problem. "Looking for similarities". A specific object or phenomenon is called, for example "helicopter". Write helicopter-like objects according to the different symbols. Similar objects can be grouped according to their characteristics. For example, "bird", "butterfly" (flying, landing), "bus", "train" (car), etc. The purpose of this is to determine the properties of objects and classify them according to signs.

"Methods of drug use". A familiar word is given, for example: "book". The extent of the most unusual use of the substance must be noted. Reads a book, can put something under it, can hide necessary papers as an object, etc. You can also offer a toothbrush, knitting yarn, etc. But it is forbidden to talk about the ways of using things in an inhuman, predatory way. "Make a sentence". Get 3 unrelated words. For example, "lake", "pen", "bear". It is necessary to form a sentence from these words. The answer can be simple (The bear dropped the pencil in the lake). The likes are then analyzed. Creative sentences are encouraged. "Find the unnecessary word". All 3 words are given. For example "dog", "summer", "sun". There are 2 words with similar characters and the unnecessary word should be deleted. This similarities between the remaining two words should be mentioned more than the difference between the omitted word. For example, the word "dog" is unnecessary, the words "summer", "Sun" remain because they: round, yellow, give energy to a person. Unusual special decisions are made (clouds, cotton, fruits, etc.) With the help of such psychological methods, students' interest in the subject increases during training, thinking develops, creativity and talent appear. In short, it can be stated that in order to develop the thought processes of students in the learning process, it is necessary to organize the above practical exercises. In conclusion, practical exercises not only the students' knowledge, but bring them closer to each other, bring out friendship, morality and hard work; leads to systematic thinking, expansion of vocabulary, sharpening of imagination.

List of used literature:

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